

JOB SATISFACTION AS THE PREDICTOR OF ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG TEACHER EDUCATORS

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine how much job satisfaction predicted organizational commitment among the teacher educators of Murshidabad district. In this study, the researcher selected 150 teacher educators as the sample from among fifteen teacher training institutions using purposive sampling technique. Two hypotheses guided the study. Organizational Commitment Scale for the Teacher Educators developed by the researcher himself and Teacher's Job Satisfaction Questionnaire developed by Nasrin and A. Annes (2014) were administered on 150 teacher educators using simple random sampling technique. P.C.C and S.M.R were the statistical techniques used by the investigator to analyse the data. The researcher found linear correlation between organizational commitment and job satisfaction ($r = .202, p < .05$) and it was also found that job satisfaction emerged as the most significant contributing variable in influencing the organizational commitment as its contribution is 4.1% of the variance ($R^2 = .041, F = 6.321, p < 0.05$).

Keywords: *Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Educators*

1. Introduction:

In terms of the conceptual framework of organisational commitment, it is necessary to comprehend the relationship between people and organisations. The management and behavioural sciences frequently recognise organisational commitment as a crucial component of the interaction between people and organisations. In the fields of organisational behaviour and human resources management, particular employees' attitudes about job satisfaction and

organisational commitment are of great interest. The investigator tried to find out in this article whether job satisfaction is related with organizational commitment or not, along with the role that Job satisfaction plays as a key predictor of organizational commitment.

Organizational commitment is the desire to stay with an organisation, the feeling of dedication to that organisation, and the willingness to put in a lot of effort on its behalf. There are three components to organizational namely affective, continuance, and normative commitment. An emotional bond with the organisation is known as affective commitment. A more logical comparison of the expenses of staying versus leaving an organisation is a feature of continuance commitment. Normative commitment refers to the ethical duty to remain with the organization. Employees' subjective response to their work is reflected in their feelings and attitude towards it, which is known as job satisfaction. The researcher found that Job satisfaction is positively related with organizational commitment, who also found that job satisfaction influences teacher educators' organisational commitment. According to Tai et al. (1998) job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a strong correlation. Markovits et al. (2010) found affective organizational commitment has the greatest impact on both intrinsic and extrinsic job satisfaction levels.

2. Conceptual Framework:

2.1 Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction can be defined as “the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs” (Spector, 1997). As per this definition, job satisfaction refers to the overall emotional satisfaction an individual derives from their job. Conversely, when someone evaluates their work experience against their expectations and feels positively about it, it is referred to as job satisfaction (Locke 1969). Previous studies have proposed that an individual's job satisfaction is derived from their feelings rather than whether their needs are met or not (Locke, 1976).

Extrinsically satisfied employees, as opposed to those intrinsically satisfied, find contentment through external means, such as monetary rewards or material perks, in exchange for adapting their behaviour. If there is no outward benefit to an employee other than the task itself, they are satisfied intrinsically. Job satisfaction is the favourable emotional condition stemming from evaluating the alignment of one's professional life with personal values. Studies indicate that job satisfaction significantly influences psychological well-being, work performance, absenteeism, and employee turnover. Additionally, according to Lee (1988), one of the best indicators of turnover is job dissatisfaction. However, a number of factors that

influence job satisfaction have been researched over time, such as pay, chances for growth, leadership style, atmosphere at work, organisational structure, and climate (Testa, 1999).

2.2 Organizational commitment

Organizational commitment measures the strength of an employee's bond with the organization, their alignment with its objectives, and their willingness to persist as an integral part of it. According to Levy's (2003) interpretation, organizational commitment refers to how much an individual aligns them with and actively participates in the functioning of the organization. Organisational behaviourists have focused a lot of attention on organizational commitment (Allen and Meyer, 1990).

Employee's subjective assessment organizational commitment encompasses their perceptions of alignment with their organization's core values, their intent to continue their tenure and their readiness to exceed typical job requirements (Mowday et al., 1979). A commitment to continuation is the dedication that staff members feel to the organisation as a result of their financial contributions or the expenses involved in giving up the job. The distinction between employees with high levels of affective and continuance commitment is that the former remain with the company because they want to stay with the organization while the latter do so out of necessity.

Organizational commitment is a concept that has been defined and measured a lot, and it has been recognised as an intriguing variable. According to Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran (2005), organizational commitment encompasses the mental inclination of an individual that ties them to a particular course of action pertaining to one or more targets, as well as their determination to continue with that course of action.

3. Objectives of the Study:

1. To found out whether job satisfaction and organizational commitment are correlated or not.
2. To find out how job satisfaction affect organizational commitment of teacher educators.

4. Hypothesis of the Study:

H₁ There will be no significant relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction of teacher educators.

H₂ There will be no significant effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment of teacher educators.

5. Methodology:

The researcher employed a descriptive design for the study. The descriptive survey method was adopted for this study. This design was deemed appropriate because it makes evaluation of existing relationship between the depended and independent variable as well as the influence of independent on depended variable on the basis of factual information collected through the use of questionnaire.

5.1 Population and Sample:

The study's population comprises all teacher educators employed within both governmental and private teacher education institutions located in the Murshidabad district. The sample comprises 150 teacher educators from 15 different teacher education institutions. The investigator selected the teacher education institutions purposively and then questionnaires were administered on the teacher educators randomly.

5.2 Variables of the Study:

The investigator took two variables for this study namely organizational commitment and job satisfaction. The researcher treated organizational commitment as the depended variable and job satisfaction as the independent variable.

Figure 1: Variables of the Study

5.3 Research Tools:

- ❖ Organizational Commitment Scale developed by the researcher himself.
- ❖ Teaher's Job Satisfaction Qustionnaire developed by Nasrin and A. Annes (2014) .

Figure 2: Tools Used in the Study

5.4 Statistical Techniques:

Stepwise multiple regression and co-efficient correlation were statistical techniques that the researcher employed to analyse and interpret the data.

6. Analysis and Interpretation of the Data:

Objective 1

To found out whether job satisfaction and organizational commitment are correlated or not.

The researcher formulated the following null hypothesis, which is presented as follows, in order to fulfil objective-1

H₀1

There will be no significant relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction of teacher educators.

The researcher treated organizational commitment as the dependent variable, and job satisfaction as independent variable, in order to attain the aforementioned objective. The P.C.C was employed to investigate whether the correlation exists between the dependent variable and the independent variable and reveal the outcomes. In the table, tabular representations of the calculated values of correlation between the dependent and independent variable for the sample of teacher educators are shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Correlation between the Criterion and Predictive Variables among Teacher Educators.

	Dependent Variable (Organizational Commitment)
Independent Variable	Rural (N= 150)
Job Satisfaction	.202*

Significant at the 0.05 level of significance

Table 1 clearly indicates organizational commitment and job satisfaction of teacher educators are significantly correlated. It is also clear from the table 1 that this correlation is positive and significant at the 0.05 level of significance,

Figure 3: The Scatter Plot of Coefficient Correlation between O.C and J.S of Teacher Educators.

As per the data presented in the table, there exists a correlation coefficient between job satisfaction of teacher educators and organizational commitment, where $r = .202$, $p < .05$ which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, according to Cohen's (1988) criteria for effect size, the Pearson correlation coefficient value ($r = .214$) reveals a moderate degree of correlation between organizational commitment and job satisfaction among teacher educators, which is also shown in figure- 3 as the line's direction is positive and data points are dispersed around the line of best fit, for the rural sample.

Therefore, we can draw a conclusion from the above discussion that organizational commitment is significantly correlated with job satisfaction at the 0.05 level of significance and the null hypothesis H_0 4 "There will be no significant relationship between the dependent

variable i.e. organizational commitment and independent variable i.e. job satisfaction of teacher educators” is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance.

Objective 2

To find out how job satisfaction affect organizational commitment of teacher educators.

Hypothesis 2

There will be no significant effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment of teacher educators.

Using stepwise multiple linear regression analysis, the above stated hypothesis was tested.

The following table represents the relevant data:

Table 2: Model Summary of SMR

Predictive Variables	R	R ²	R ² Change	F- Change	P- Value
Job Satisfaction	.202	.041	.041	6.321**	0.013

From the above table-2, it is quite evident that R is used in the model to represents the observed and predicted values of dependent variable are correlated which is found to be .202. Thus, in this model, it shows the correlation between the organizational commitment reported by the male teacher educators and organizational commitment predicted for the teacher educators by this predicted variable i.e. job satisfaction.

Table 3: summary of ANOVA for Regression Analysis

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P- value
Regression	929.064	1	929.064	6.321*	.013
Residual	21753.309	148	146.982		
Total	22682.373	149			

In the model, the magnitude of predictability is represented by R² and the table-2 and table-3 shows the results of the regression that clearly indicates one predictor explained 4.1% of the variance (R² = .041, F = 6.321, p<0.05). Thus, the analysis of the table-2 and table-3 reveal that job satisfaction is found as significant predictor of organizational commitment for the teacher educators. From the table-2 it is also evident that job satisfaction emerged as the most significant contributing variable in influencing the organizational commitment as its contribution is 4.1% which can be explained as R² Change = .041, F = 6.321, p<0.05.

Table 4: Co-efficient Regression Analysis

Predictive variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t- Value	P- Value
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	96.719	10.996		8.795**	.000
Job Satisfaction	.167	..066	.202	2.514*	.013

Figure 4: Percentage Contribution of Predictive Variables on the Criterion Variable i.e. Organizational Commitment of Teacher Educators.

Table-4 reveals that the standardized coefficient, including the t-value for the predictor job satisfaction, is positive and statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. The Table-4 shows that job satisfaction ($\beta = .202$, $t = 514$, $p < 0.05$) has the strong predicting power in predicting the organizational commitment of teacher educators. Thus, it shows that an increase in per unit in job satisfaction, the organizational commitment of teacher educators increases by .167. Thus, this predictive variable is positive and significant, indicating that the variance due to this predictor will cause a positive and significant change in the organizational commitment.

Here the effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis “There will be no significant effect of job

satisfaction on organizational commitment of teachers educators” is rejected at the 0.05 level of significance.

7. Findings:

The researcher found linear correlation between organizational commitment and job satisfaction ($r = .202$, $p < .05$) of teacher educators which is significant at .05 level of significance.

The investigator discovered that job satisfaction emerged as the most significant contributing variable in influencing the organizational commitment as its contribution is 4.1% of the variance ($R^2 = .041$, $F = 6.321$, $p < 0.05$) for the teacher educators.

8. Conclusions

Therefore, we can draw a conclusion from the above discussion that organizational commitment is significantly correlated with job satisfaction of teacher educators at the .05 level of significance and they are positively correlated that means organizational commitment of teacher educators will increase as their job satisfaction increases.

The findings also lead us to the conclusion that the effect of job satisfaction on organizational commitment is significant at the 0.05 level of significance. It means for the sample of teacher educators predictive variable job satisfaction can be used to predict their organizational commitment. It shows that the contribution of this predictive variable i.e. job satisfaction on the criterion variable i.e. organizational commitment cannot occur by chance.

9. Implication:

According to the study's findings, job satisfaction is a key indicator of organizational commitment. Hence the teacher educators would be more committed to their institutions when they would be more satisfied with their job. Thus, it is suggested that the authorities, administrators, and the government should take the required steps to enhance job satisfaction. A specific time period must be allotted for faculty members to meet with administrators and have the opportunity to talk about any problems or concerns. For the benefit of the faculty members and the institutions in general, it should be encouraged to make healthy suggestions. By improving the working conditions for teacher educators, all of these should be emphasized.

In order to improve job satisfaction, the government, policymakers, and administrators should reform some related factors. Further contemporary training and development programmes may be introduced for making the teacher educator more efficient at their work. Adequate salary should be provided on time, ideal student teacher ratio should be maintained, vacant

seats for the faculty members should be fulfilled on time. Thus all these measures will encourage the teacher educators to attentive, dedicated, hard worker and committed to their institutions in the best academic interest.

Teachers educators' commitment would be negatively impacted by job stress and irritation caused by an excessive workload, a strict schedule, and unpaid time off for necessary tasks, thus it is important to take all possible steps to prevent such circumstances.

10. Suggestions for the Further Research:

10.1 The study can be extended to other regions of the country, as it was only conducted in the district of West Bengal. Therefore, it is advised that comparable research be done in other areas and districts of the country.

10.2 Principals, administrators, teachers from elementary, middle, and high schools, faculty from public and private colleges, and teachers from universities can also be taken as samples because only teacher educators were included in the present study's population.

10.3 Studies of this nature may be encouraged to use a variety of study areas, populations, and data gathering techniques and methods.

10.4 Further research on other psychological variables can be conducted as just one independent variable was used in the current study. The variance in the organisational commitment of the teacher educators may therefore be due to some other possible variables.

10.5 The nature of the current study is quantitative. As a result, it is proposed that the study can be conducted using mix method, i.e., quantitative and qualitative.

List of Abbreviations:

O.C	Organizational Commitment
J.S	Job Satisfaction
P.C.C	Pearson correlation coefficient
S.M.R	Stepwise Multiple Regression

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